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Deliverable D3.3: Second year report on the marketing and dissemination activities M19 to M24 (March to August 2025).

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Authors: Andrea Biancini (EITD), Romane Léauté (EITD), Domitilla Mariotti (EITD)

Abstract

This deliverable summarizes the strategies and achievements in promoting the project's goals. Key activities include creating marketing materials, participating in industry conferences, and utilizing digital platforms for outreach. The report evaluates the effectiveness of these efforts and suggests improvements for the future, aiming to enhance SPECTRO's visibility and impact. Deliverable D.3.3 represents SPECTRO's Second-Year Report on marketing and dissemination activities. In agreement with the Project Officer, the previous report (D3.2) already covered the extended first reporting period, from M1 to M18 (up to 28 February 2025), to align with the interim review. As such, D3.3 does not repeat previously reported activities and instead focuses exclusively on the second half of Project Year 2, covering the period from M19 to M24 (March to August 2025).

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1 Introduction

1.1 Project summary

SPecialised Education programmes in CybersecuriTy and Robotics (SPECTRO) focuses on the design and delivery of two double-degree master's programmes (ISCED Level 7, 120 ECTS) in two key digital technology areas for the future of Europe: Cybersecurity and Robotics.

The two specialised master's programmes, which also include a minor in Innovation and Entrepreneurship, are designed and delivered by a consortium consisting of 12 higher education institutions from 7 different countries, 2 innovative SMEs, 1 leading research centre in Information Systems and EIT Digital, a pan-European organisation with in-depth knowledge and experience in the digital skills domain. In 2025, two additional higher education institutions joined the consortium as Associated partners. The consortium now counts 14 higher education institutions from 8 different countries.

In addition to the two master's programmes, SPECTRO partners develop and deploy a series of standalone learning modules on Cybersecurity and Robotics. These modules lead to four different certifications, awarded by participating higher education institutions and EIT Digital: Cybersecurity Basics Certificate, Cybersecurity Advanced Certificate, Robotics Basics Certificate, Robotics Advanced certificate.

Marketing and dissemination employed by SPECTRO focuses on enhancing the overall understanding of the advanced fields of Cybersecurity and Robotics, fostering a constructive dialogue among higher education institutions, the workforce, and the public. The activities in WP3 are designed to effectively communicate essential details about the project, its contextual relevance, and its outcomes to both specialized stakeholders and the broader public. The overarching goal is to promote shared learning, encourage the implementation of digital advancements, and facilitate the dissemination of governance innovations.

WP3 works closely with other work packages (WP1: Curriculum Design Cybersecurity, WP2: Curriculum Design Autonomous Systems and Intelligent Robots, and WP4: Project Management) to ensure effective communication in a collaborative approach, maximizing the project's impact. By creating synergies among different components and stakeholders, WP3 contributes to a broader societal understanding and adoption of advancements in Cybersecurity and Robotics. These efforts directly influence the admissions and interests of potential and current students in the double-degree education programmes in these fields.

1.2 Deliverable overview

Deliverable 3.3 represents SPECTRO's Second-Year Report on marketing and dissemination activities. In agreement with the Project Officer, the previous report (D3.2) already covered the extended first reporting period, from M1 to M18 included (up to 28 February 2025), to align with the interim review. As such, **D3.3 does not repeat previously reported activities and instead focuses exclusively on the second half of Project Year 2, covering the period from M19 to M24 (March to August 2025)**. The project activities revolve around the development and delivery of education programmes in Cybersecurity and Robotics, namely:

- The 2 master's programmes, one in Cybersecurity and one in Robotics, each span two years and are double-degree programmes (ISCED Level 7, 120 ECTS). Both programmes offer students a minor in Innovation and Entrepreneurship (I&E) totalling 30 ECTS, including a summer course on transforming innovative digital technologies into business between the first and second years of the master's programmes.
- At least 12 standalone learning modules on topics related to Cybersecurity and Robotics, including dedicated sections on Innovation and Entrepreneurship and Ethics for Trustworthy Technology, are available for free. These modules target a much broader audience than the master's programmes and lead to certifications. Participants can follow different paths through the modules, resulting in four different certifications.

For details on the Marketing and Dissemination plan and strategy, please consult Deliverable 3.1 Report presenting the Marketing and Dissemination Plan for SPECTRO project. The communication and dissemination efforts for the SPECTRO project utilize a range of marketing strategies and channels to increase awareness about the project and the educational offerings developed under the SPECTRO framework. These efforts aim to engage relevant stakeholders for promotional purposes and enhance the long-term sustainability of the deliverables. Various communication channels, including online platforms, social media, newsletters, articles, and targeted outreach to industry networks and associations, are employed to reach the target audience. Dedicated marketing campaigns are launched to recruit students into the education programmes while promoting diversity by encouraging the participation of women and individuals from RIS countries.

For details on the project's First Eighteen-Months Report on marketing and dissemination activities (M1-M18), please consult Deliverable 3.2.

The communication and dissemination strategy are translated into a set of dissemination actions and promotional campaigns, implemented via the project's communication channels and those of its partners to maximize impact. These efforts follow the objectives outlined below:

- **DO1. Raise awareness.** Ensure that the key results are disseminated (spread and understood) among the target audiences of the project.
- **DO2. Engage key stakeholders.** Maintain the engagement of the involved stakeholders across related projects and further engage other actors vital to or benefiting the outreach.
- **DO3. Enhance sustainability long-term.** Maintain effective collaboration of key stakeholders during and after the project's lifetime.

The document delivers an overview of the activities undertaken during M19-M24, channels employed, and results achieved up to this point. Conclusively, it analyses marketing and dissemination activities to draw insights into optimal approaches moving forward and identify areas for improvement. All SPECTRO consortium partners support marketing and dissemination activities by providing content, participating in events, and promoting the project outcomes.

2 Communication and Dissemination Framework: Progress and Updates

2.1 Timeline

The Gantt Chart included in Deliverable D3.1 outlines the planned timeline for communication and dissemination activities throughout the SPECTRO project. It maps key actions and milestones for promoting the project, engaging target audiences, and sharing updates and results. During M19-M24, activities were implemented in alignment with this plan. As the project progresses closes its second year, the Gantt Chart remains an important tool to guide, coordinate, and enhance the effectiveness of communication efforts with accuracy.

2.2 Branding

A unified branding and visual communication structure was developed and continuously refined to meet evolving project needs while ensuring alignment with the guidelines established in D3.1 (Marketing and Dissemination Activities Plan, Section 4.1). This structure ensured consistency across all SPECTRO dissemination and marketing activities, including a cohesive visual identity—colour scheme, logos, and templates—applied to presentations, campaigns, deliverables, and digital platforms. Custom graphics and tailored visuals were designed to effectively communicate project goals and progress to diverse audiences. The branding approach remained consistent yet adaptable, supporting a strong and recognisable presence

throughout the project's second year. Examples of dissemination materials are provided in Section 3.4 Creation of dissemination materials.

2.3 SPECTRO webpage

The SPECTRO webpage still serves as the central hub for all project-related information, including details on the consortium, short-term courses, published public deliverables, available scholarships, news, and upcoming events. The content is regularly updated to reflect the latest developments, for example all self-standing modules have been listed to the webpage.

Self-standing online modules: Cybersecurity and Robotics

The SPECTRO online modules in Robotics and Cybersecurity are a flexible, self-paced learning experience designed by leading experts in the field. Whether you're looking to deepen your technical knowledge or explore new domains, these innovative online courses offer practical, up-to-date content tailored to your learning needs. Each module can be taken independently, with a certificate of completion awarded upon successful assessment. For learners seeking a more comprehensive achievement, completing a curated set of modules leads to a Basics or Advanced certification in Robotics or Cybersecurity. The courses are hosted on the [SPECTRO online learning platform](#) powered by Icarus.

More online topics and online courses are also available on the [EIT Digital Icarus Education online learning platform](#).

CYBERSECURITY, ROBOTICS, INNOVATION & ENTREPRENEURSHIP COURSES (SPECTRO)	
Course name	Topic
Basic Concepts of Cryptography	CyberSecurity
Cyber Security for the Business User	CyberSecurity
Ethical Hacking Course on Web Application Security	CyberSecurity
Foundations of Cyber Security	CyberSecurity

Figure 1: Screenshot from the SPECTRO webpage

2.4 SPECTRO summer schools

The Summer School plays a key role in fostering student mobility by bringing participants to a new country, where they are immersed in an international and multicultural environment. Beyond the academic curriculum, students have the opportunity to interact and collaborate with peers from other programmes, which broadens their perspectives and builds a strong network across disciplines. The experience also exposes them to the local

culture through organised activities and informal exchanges, allowing them to gain insights into different ways of living and working.

From a communication and dissemination perspective, summer schools also generate significant visibility for the SPECTRO programmes. Professors, organisers, and students frequently share posts before, during, and after the summer school on platforms such as LinkedIn, creating a dynamic flow of content that highlights the academic and cultural dimensions of the experience. These authentic testimonials and on-the-ground updates not only increase outreach to prospective students and stakeholders but also position SPECTRO as an active and vibrant educational community.

Cycle 1 SPECTRO Summer schools were the following:

- AI-Driven Cybersecurity, University of Rennes, France (Jun 29–Jul 12, 2025)
- Digital Platforms for Smart Cities, University of Aalto, Helsinki, Finland (11-22 August 2025)

Alvaro Pina Stranger ✓ · 1er

Associate Professor of Management

1 mois · 🌐

...

Good things also come to an end!
 But these two weeks with our students were the perfect way to kick off the summer break.
 The group was a wonderful mix of talent, kindness, and empathy.
 Thank you all for making the most of the time we spent together.
 Enjoy your summer — and everything that follows in your studies.
 I hope to see you again at the graduation ceremony, just over a year from now!

Many thanks to our jury members: [Adèle Hamon](#) [Barbara Hegyi Ph.D.](#) [Marie Corbin](#) [Pierre-Alain Fouque](#) [Franz Regu](#) [Viktoria Villanyi](#) [Alexia Froud](#) [kine](#) 🇪🇺

[#AldrivenCybersecurity](#) [#Innovation](#) [Université de Rennes](#) [ISTIC UFR Informatique-Électronique](#) [@EU_HaDEA](#) [#SPECTRO](#) [#DigitalEUProgramme](#)

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👍❤️👏 Vilma Djala et 122 autres personnes

4 commentaires · 16 republications

Figure 2: LinkedIn post (1) about the SPECTRO summer school in Rennes

EIT Digital
44 335 abonnés
1 mois · 🌐

And with that, we say "Au Revoir!" to the EIT Digital SPECTRO Summer School hosted by [Université de Rennes!](#) 🙌🇫🇷

Thanks for an incredible two weeks, where the students dived into the world of AI-driven cybersecurity innovations to unlock the future of deep-tech venture creation!

Over the program, it gave students the chance to:

- 📖 Focus: AI-driven cybersecurity & cybersecurity of AI
- 🧠 Build critical assessment & entrepreneurial skills
- 🚀 Turn cutting-edge tech into market-ready solutions

We hope everyone had a fantastic time!

Stay tuned here and on Instagram (@eit_digital) for updates as our Summer Schools in Barcelona, Ljubljana and Madrid continue for their second week. 📱

[European Health and Digital Executive Agency \(HaDEA\)](#)

[#HaDEA](#) [#DigitalEUProgramme](#) [#DigitalEurope](#) [#SPECTRO](#) [#euprojects](#) [#study](#)

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THANKS RENNES

Figure 3: LinkedIn post (2) about the SPECTRO summer school in Rennes

EIT Digital Master School
 954 abonnés
 22 h · Modifié ·

Thanks Helsinki and [Aalto University](#) for an inspiring two weeks in Finland. 🙏

We've been able to see first hand how the participants got to grips with the themes of:

- Smart cities
- Platform economy
- Data economy and sustainability
- Launching a platform and competitiveness
- Intelligent platform strategy
- Modeling platforms and designing ecosystems

We know that this is only the beginning and we cannot wait for the next step 🚀

Massive thanks to everyone involved over the past few weeks [Mike Bradshaw](#), [Anastasia Koptsyukh](#) 🇺🇸, [Duy Tran](#), [Olli-Pekka Mutanen](#), [Anna Kurmaeva](#), [Lea Myyryläinen](#), [Teemu Ropponen](#), [Indrajit Chaudhuri](#), [Marko Turpeinen](#), [Erik Liesola](#), [Marco Steinberg](#), [Miloš N Mladenović](#), [Monika Liikamaa](#), [Janne Lautanala](#), [Ohto Pentikäinen](#), [Tomi Paalosmaa](#), [Lucy Truong](#), [Nithin Nadagouda](#), [Pauliina Alanen](#), [Tanya Sahdev](#), [Paul Wong](#), [Utshav Bhattarai](#) [Mikko Kaipainen](#) and [Patrik Fjällberg](#).

[European Health and Digital Executive Agency \(HaDEA\)](#)
 #SPECTRO #euprojects #cybersecurity #studyineurope #robotics #Training #

Figure 4: LinkedIn Post (3) about the SPECTRO summer school in Helsinki

2.5 SPECTRO platform for Robotics and Cybersecurity self-standing modules

2.5.1 SPECTRO online platform for self-standing courses

The SPECTRO WP3 leader, in collaboration with project partner Evolutionary Archetypes (EA), has successfully designed and launched a dedicated online platform to host SPECTRO’s self-standing modules in Cybersecurity and Robotics. The platform, aligned with the project’s visual identity, is fully operational and currently hosts almost 200 registered learners. It offers a user-friendly experience for self-paced learning, with dedicated areas for instructors to upload course content and manage evaluations. A recent visual and structural update has enhanced the platform’s navigation by clearly distinguishing focus areas—Cybersecurity, Robotics, Innovation & Entrepreneurship —and their respective course offerings.

SPECTRO Cybersecurity Courses

<p>Foundations of Cyber Security 14 Lessons Antti Hakkala</p>			
<p>Offensive Security: Applications and... 13 Lessons Florian Hahn</p>			

SPECTRO Robotics Courses

FREE

10 Lessons

Artificial Intelligence for Intelligent Robots

Zoltán Istenes

FREE

19 Lessons

Autonomous Multi-Agent Systems

Mihhail Matskin

FREE

0 Lessons

Distributed Autonomous Systems

Giuseppe Notarstefano

FREE

9 Lessons

Introduction to Computer Vision

Marton Szemenyei

FREE

15 Lessons

Introduction to Industrial Robotics

Emese Gincsal Szadeczky-Kardoss

FREE

2 Lessons

Introduction to Mobile Robotics in Industry

Tommaso Faraci

FREE

10 Lessons

Introduction to Software Engineering Methods

Mihhail Matskin

FREE

5 Lessons

Miniaturised Robots and Micromanipulation

Zhou Quan

SPECTRO Innovation & Entrepreneurship and Ethics Courses

FREE

13 Lessons

Academic Ethics and Integrity in Computer...

Simona Motogna

FREE

12 Lessons

Business Development 1 – What is a business?

Giorgio Scartion

FREE

12 Lessons

Business Development 2 – How to develop a...

Caterina Trevisan

FREE

11 Lessons

Innovation Management & Digital Economy...

Alexandru Roja

FREE

22 Lessons

Introduction to Agile Project Management

Dan-Mircea Suci

Figure 5: SPECTRO online learning platform, landing page updated

2.5.2 Self-standing modules certificates design

As part of the development of the SPECTRO self-standing modules, two types of certificates were designed and implemented to recognise learners' achievements. The first certificate (Figure 6) is awarded upon completion of a single self-standing module and is tailored for professional use, particularly on social media platforms such as LinkedIn, allowing learners to showcase specific skills acquired. The second certificate (Figure 7) corresponds to the completion of a series of modules grouped under either the "Basics" or "Advanced" certification tracks in Cybersecurity or Robotics. This certification adheres to academic standards and provides a more comprehensive validation of learning, intended for formal recognition by educational institutions and employers alike.

Figure 6: SPECTRO certificate of completion of a single module (template version)

THE SPECTRO PROJECT PARTNERS AND EIT DIGITAL AWARD THIS CERTIFICATE TO

FULLNAME

TITLE: Cybersecurity Basic / Cybersecurity Advanced / Robotics Basic / Robotics Advanced

This is to certify that the participant has successfully completed all listed courses and passed the corresponding assessments, including the final evaluation.

Federico Menna
CEO, EIT Digital

TOMORROW'S DIGITAL INNOVATORS
AND ENTREPRENEURS

Figure 7: SPECTRO “Basic/Advanced” certificate (template version)

2.6 Dissemination channel strategy: creation of a SPECTRO

LinkedIn page

As the SPECTRO project advances, a dedicated LinkedIn page was launched in July 2025 to strengthen dissemination efforts and expand the project’s outreach. This page will serve as a central hub to communicate SPECTRO’s milestones, achievements, and opportunities to a wide audience, including professionals, industry experts, EU and national institutions, universities, professors, and the general public. While partners will continue leveraging their institutional and personal social media accounts, the LinkedIn page will act as a relay for their messages, offering a unified and consistent presence. The decentralized approach has posed challenges in reporting, particularly in tracking engagement and the inconsistent use of agreed hashtags, making the

LinkedIn page a strategic solution to streamline communication, enhance visibility, and serve as a reliable window into the project. The page currently counts 43 subscribers.

Figure 8: SPECTRO LinkedIn page

Figure 9: Repost on the SPECTRO LinkedIn page

2.6.1 Management and coordination

The management of the LinkedIn page is overseen by the WP3 Communication Coordinator, who is responsible for ensuring consistency and relevance of content. This includes planning, publishing, and monitoring activities on the platform. The Communication Coordinator acts as the main point of contact for all partners, collecting inputs and transforming them into engaging posts. Regular monitoring of activity and engagement helps adjust the strategy when necessary and ensures the page remains active and relevant.

2.6.2 Editorial calendar and Partner contributions

To organize the flow of content, an editorial calendar has been introduced. This calendar defines the publication dates and the type of content to be shared, creating a structured approach to communication. Partners are encouraged to contribute regularly by proposing news, updates on project activities, announcements of events, or dissemination of scientific outputs. The LinkedIn page serves as an amplification tool for the partners'

dissemination actions, acting as a unified window into the SPECTRO project and its achievements. Editorial planning and discussion of upcoming content take place during WP3 monthly coordination meetings, ensuring that all partners are aligned and that the content pipeline is maintained effectively.

2.7 WP3 Monthly coordination meetings

Monthly coordination meetings serve as a check point for aligning communication and dissemination activities across the SPECTRO consortium. All partners, including their designated communication contact points, are invited to participate. These sessions are chaired by the Communication Coordinator, who provides updates on ongoing and upcoming dissemination actions, news, and relevant developments.

During each meeting, partners review planned campaigns, contribute suggestions, and share news items that can be highlighted through project channels. The Communication Coordinator also presents newly developed dissemination materials, ensuring partners are equipped with consistent and branded resources. Additionally, these meetings provide support where partners can raise questions, request assistance, or seek advice on specific communication-related needs.

Finally, partners use this opportunity to share an overview of upcoming events in their respective organizations or networks, which are then integrated into the project's dissemination plan to maximize visibility and outreach.

3 Organic social media promotion activities

In the context of organic outreach, with a specific focus on raising awareness for SPECTRO, social media channels play a key role in the project's communication and dissemination activities. These channels have the potential to significantly enhance post visibility and topic exposure through impressions, creating opportunities for increased reach and content visibility.

Content targets the following stakeholder clusters:

- Current and prospective master students,
- summer-school candidates and attendees,
- lifelong learners looking for short online modules,
- the wider cybersecurity & robotics community that can amplify the messages.
- The general public, civil society, European and national public institutions.

The organic social media communication strategy is managed by the Communication Coordinator, who ensures that content aligns with the recruitment and learning objectives of the programme. Activities are executed

primarily on LinkedIn and other relevant platforms such as Instagram, following a calendar that reflects ongoing initiatives throughout the academic year.

Themes and messaging are defined according to upcoming events and programme priorities. Visual and textual materials are prepared to maintain consistency with SPECTRO and EIT Digital branding. Posts are then scheduled to ensure regular engagement and optimal timing for audience reach. Coordination with partners and internal stakeholders is essential to gather relevant content, such as updates on the Master School, Summer Schools, and online learning opportunities. Organic engagement is encouraged by highlighting success stories, student experiences, and programme benefits. The publication timeline is nonetheless indicative and serves as a reference for coordinated actions; partners are strongly encouraged to complement these efforts by promoting their own SPECTRO-related activities through their channels, ensuring broader outreach and engagement.

The timeline for social media activities between M19 and M24 (March to August 2025) was distributed as follows:

- From March to June, the focus was on promoting the EIT Digital Master School and supporting the final stages of the recruitment cycle, ensuring prospective students were informed and encouraged to apply.
- In June and July, the campaign shifted to highlight the Summer School, providing visibility to its activities and attracting participants.
- Finally, during July and August, the emphasis moved to online module promotion, targeting individuals interested in using the summer period for professional development and upskilling.

3.1.1 Social media organic promotion

SPECTRO project partners play an active role in amplifying the project's visibility by leveraging their institutional social media channels and internal communication networks. Their efforts include regular updates, engaging content, and targeted campaigns on platforms such as LinkedIn, Facebook, and Instagram, aiming to connect with prospective students, industry stakeholders, and academic communities. The SPECTRO LinkedIn page serves as a central hub and catalyst for these activities, acting as a one-stop showcase for the project by consolidating news, programme information, and success stories in a single, easily accessible location. This coordinated approach ensures that content shared by individual partners reinforces the project's overall visibility strategy, while the LinkedIn page provides a unified point of reference.

 EIT Digital Master School
851 abonnés
2 j. • 🌐

While many of you have already experienced the power of EIT Digital education and are well versed in our courses, we're proud to offer, in partnership with the European Union's Digital Europe Programme, 13 stand-alone modules in Cybersecurity. 🇪🇺 📖 🛡️

Developed in collaboration with top-tier universities and innovation partners across Europe, these programmes are designed to:

- 🔍 Equip students with skills to protect sensitive health data
- 🧠 Explore the intersection of AI, diagnostics, and secure data systems
- 🌐 Train tech talent ready to build trustworthy digital health solutions across Europe

🎓 Already part of the EIT Digital community? Here's how you can help:

- 🗣️ Spread the word to aspiring tech and cybersecurity minds
- 👥 Tag a friend passionate about digital health or data protection

Learn more and explore the Cybersecurity modules 🖱️
<https://okt.to/BvcAjf>

European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HaDEA)

[#SPECTRO](#) [#euprojects](#) [#cybersecurity](#) [#studyineurope](#) [#robotics](#) [#Trainir](#)

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Figure 10: LinkedIn post promoting the SPECTRO Cybersecurity online modules

Evolutionary Archetypes Consulting SL + Suivre ...
 503 abonnés
 1 sem. •

😊 We're thrilled to see the launch of the new edition of the **EIT Digital Master School SPECTRO Summer School** in Rennes, France!

The launch event featured keynote sessions by **Thiébaut Meyer** and **Léa Deswarte**.
 This AI-driven cybersecurity program brings together tomorrow's cyber and robotics leaders.
 Looking forward to witnessing the next generation of cyber- and robotics experts in action.

Learn more about SPECTRO: <https://lnkd.in/gFahyADm>

#EITDigital #SPECTRO #Cybersecurity #Robotics #EducationInnovation #Alle

<https://lnkd.in/g8mhMJSB>

Afficher la traduction

Alvaro Pina Stranger • 1er
 Associate Professor of Management
 3 sem. • Modifié •

Very happy to have started today a new edition of our **EIT Digital Master School Spectro Summer School**.
 Thank you to our keynotes: **Thiébaut Meyer** and **Léa Deswarte**, to our VP **Sébastien LE PICARD** and our Innovation manager **François Huber** :-)
 and to all students for their courageous engagement under this very hot weather!

#AldrivenCybersecurity #innovation
Université de Rennes ISTIC UFR
Informatique-Électronique @EU_HaDEA #SPECTRO #DigitalEUProgramme

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Figure 11: SPECTRO Summer school launch, LinkedIn post

Figure 12: EIT Digital Master School's LinkedIn page reposting a student's comment on the SPECTRO Summer School

Figure 13: EIT Digital posting about the SPECTRO Summer School

Figure 14: Evolutionary Archetypes post on Instagram

3.2 Social media Paid campaigns

Presentation of paid social media campaigns for the Master school and the self standing modules: March 2025 to August 2025.

3.2.1 Google Search Paid Ads

There were no Google Search Paid Ads between M19 and M24 (March – August 2025).

3.2.2 REDDIT Paid Ads

Following the decision made in January 2025 to include REDDIT as one of the channels used to promote SPECTRO, its programs and courses, paid campaigns have been running on the platform since. From March 2025 until May 2025, our efforts were focused on the Master School program Autonomous Systems and Intelligent

Robots. Three ads with the same visuals ran, having different audiences in mind: REDDIT’s Broad Communities, Niche Communities and Interest Communities. The goal of these campaigns was student recruitment.

<input type="checkbox"/> Off/On	Name	Status	Impressions	Clicks
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Creative 1: Build Your Own Dance Partner	Not delivering	581,168	3,463

Figure 15: Broad Communities campaign, numbers from March 2025 to May 2025

<input type="checkbox"/> Off/On	Name	Status	Impressions	Clicks
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Creative 1: Build Your Own Dance Partner	Not delivering	311,128	1,041

Figure 16: Niche Communities campaign, numbers from March 2025 to May 2025

<input type="checkbox"/> Off/On	Name	Status	Impressions	Clicks
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Creative 1: Build Your Own Dance Partner	Not delivering	614,025	4,616

Figure 17: Interest Communities campaign, numbers from March 2025 to May 2025

Starting from August 2025, there's an ongoing campaign to attract interested parties to the self-standing modules, which include short courses for cybersecurity, robotics, and innovation and entrepreneurship. These courses are free for all and offer a wide range of knowledge, starting from any base. These campaigns have also been divided on two different REDDIT Communities: Broad Communities and Key Word Targeting.

<input type="checkbox"/> Off/On	Name	Status	Impressions	Clicks
<input type="checkbox"/>	Spectro Broad Communities	: Active	424,239	1,264
<input type="checkbox"/>	Spectro KW Targeting Q3 2025	: Active	364,742	1,152

Figure 18: Impressions and clicks for self-standing module campaign up to 31 August 2025

Figure 19: cover of the self-standing module ad

3.3 Dissemination of information through events and conferences

During March–August 2025, the project EITD WP3 team and the project partners attended 11 events, conferences and fairs, reaching out to over 2,000 persons in total. At most of these events, the SPECTRO project had a dedicated booth, space, or visual presence, showcasing the project outcomes.

Most of the promotional and recruitment activities for SPECTRO took place in Fall 2025 and were reported in Deliverable 3.2. The spring period (March–May 2025) focused primarily on local university events and a few conferences, aimed at maintaining visibility and engaging with specific target groups. The July–August summer months are traditionally a calm period for fairs and recruitment activities.

The table below summarizes the events attended or organised by consortium partners, March–August 2025, which collectively reached approximately 2,000 participants. The SPECTRO educational offer and project outcomes were advertised at all these events, with dedicated communication campaigns or materials.

Date	Activity Name	Who? Target audience
21/03/2025	Webinar for UBB's undergraduate students	Students
28/03/2025	UBB Master of Science Day	Students
17/04/2025	Ethical Hacking 101 – Workshop	Students
09/05/2025	2025 IEEE/ASME International Conference on Advanced Intelligent Mechatronics (AIM2025), at Hangzhou, China, July 14-18, 2025	Robotics professionals
15/05/2025	Open Days Masters' Degrees University Trento	Students
14-Jul-25	The 2025 International Conference on Manipulation, Automation and Robotics at Small Scales (MARSS 2025), at West Lafayette, USA, July 28-Aug. 01, 2025	Robotics professionals
9-Jul-25	The 49th IEEE International Conference on Computer, Software and Application (COMPSAC 2025)	Cybersecurity professionals
February 25-26, 2025	UNIBO Orientation days : event for the presentation of Bachelor's and Master's Degree to prospective students	Students
16-Apr-25	DEI Department Open day (live and online) at UNIBO	Students
11/08/2025	"Jyväskylä Summer School " at Turku	Students
20-Mar	Master Open Day University of Twente	Students

The below show examples of SPECTRO presentations at events:

- UBB's "Master Of Science Day", March 28, 2025 (see Figure 20): The event is designed and organized by the Academic School for Natural and Life Sciences which includes 6 faculties of the Babeş-Bolyai University and is dedicated to master's and bachelor's students (and anyone who wants to participate). It gathered about 300 participants. The event aims to familiarize students with projects from the multiple master's programs at these faculties and offers a unique multidisciplinary platform where students can explore projects from various fields and discuss with researchers and teaching staff in an informal setting. The program included a presentation of the SPECTRO Master's, and a session of round tables where students can interact informally with researchers and teaching staff, which included SPECTRO's.
- University Trento's "Open Days Masters' Degrees", 15 May, 2025 (see Figure 21): provided an opportunity to promote the SPECTRO programmes to prospective bachelor's students from the university. During the session, participants were introduced to the structure and unique perks of the SPECTRO Master's programmes, including the international mobility scheme, double-degree opportunities, and access to specialised courses in cybersecurity and robotics. Professors and alumni were present to share their experiences and insights, creating an interactive setting where students could ask questions directly and gain first-hand perspectives on academic content, career prospects, and the added value of joining the programme.

Figure 20: UBB's "Master Of Science Day", SPECTRO poster

Figure 21: SPECTRO presentation at the Open days Master's degrees at the University of Trento

3.4 Creation of dissemination materials

WP3 Communication Coordinator created tailored dissemination tools, and materials. Each tool and material play a role in marketing and outreach strategy by enhancing visibility, engagement, and communication with prospective students:

- Promotion Toolkit: Provides standardized resources that ensure consistency in messaging and branding across promotional activities, making it easier for project partners to promote the program effectively.

- Local Promotion Designs: Tailored materials for specific regions help address cultural preferences and local interests, increasing relevance and impact in targeted areas.
- Banners, Posters for events: Eye-catching visuals at education fairs attract attention, create a strong first impression, and provide essential information about the program to attendees.
- Thematic Campaigns for Social Media (incl. visuals, reels): Engaging and creative content on social media platforms boosts online visibility, captures the interest of a digital-savvy audience, and drives traffic to application portal.

Figure 22: “AI-Driven Cybersecurity Summer School” roll-up, for the University of Rennes

Figure 23: “EIT Digital Master School” SPECTRO posters

3.5 Publication of press releases, articles and documents

SPECTRO Coordinator and project partner regularly publish articles, blog posts and media articles to promote the project activities, share recent project news, and position the project early outcomes as a reference in scientific publications and articles.

DATE
May 12, 2025

SHARE
X f in

 Federico Guerrini
federico.guerrini@eitdigital.eu

How an innovative Finnish SME is helping shape the next generation of robotics engineers

The **SPECTRO** project, led by EIT Digital, addresses the critical need for advanced digital skills in two key technology areas: Cybersecurity and Robotics. This ambitious initiative brings together 12 higher education institutions from 7 countries, 2 innovative SMEs, a leading research centre in Information Systems, and EIT Digital. Together, the consortium is designing and delivering two double-degree master's programmes that will develop essential talent for Europe's digital future.

SPECTRO aims to support the growth of a digitalized European economy and society by empowering citizens and businesses while ensuring the security of Europe's digital supply chains. By creating specialized Master's Programmes and self-standing learning modules that lead to certifications, the project is enhancing Europe's educational offerings in these strategic fields.

Figure 26: An article on GIM Robotics on the EIT Digital website

4 Results, achievements and conclusions

4.1 KPIs and first 24-months results commented

The two tables below illustrate the results achieved during the first 24-months of the project, against the overall project benchmarks (KPIs).

KPI	Expected Result	Expected	Actual Results
	<i>Overall Project</i>	<i>First 24-months</i>	<i>First 24-months</i>
KPI20: Number of applications to the education programmes	3,500	1,750	899
KPI21: Number of master's programmes on Cybersecurity and Robotics listed on the Digital Skills and Jobs Platform	2	2	2
KPI22: Number of leads interested in the education programmes	12,000	6,000	9,215

Table 1: SPECTRO project KPIs

KPI20 Comment: The number of applications to the education programmes (including both Master's applications and learners who started a self-standing online module) reached 899, which is below the expected interim target of 1,750. This underperformance highlights the need for continued efforts in outreach and recruitment. It is expected that the number of learners engaging with the self-standing modules will increase over the coming months, contributing positively to KPI20.

KPI21 Comment: The project has met its expected target for this KPI, achieving the listing of two master's programmes in the first months of the project.

KPI22 Comment: With 9,215 leads collected, SPECTRO achieved over 150% of the interim target of 6,000. This figure was obtained by aggregating diverse channels of interest, including applications started, webinar attendance, contact requests, lead generation forms, and accounts created on the self-standing course platform.

The 24-month impact achieved presented in the Table 2 below was measured as follows: the impact of SPECTRO webpages and social media activities—both organic and paid—is measured using analytics tools that track the total number of visitors, impressions, and clicks over a given period. These raw totals are then broken down into a simplified, linear monthly average to provide a consistent and comparable view of performance across time. While actual activity varies—some months see higher engagement due to specific campaigns or events—this average offers a practical way to assess communication impact in a structured manner, with comparable figures to the overall project expected impact.

ACTIVITY CHANNEL	Expected Impact <i>Overall project</i>	Impact Achieved <i>First 24-months</i>
CH1. SPECTRO webpages	10,000/month visitors	13,285/month visitors (3 pages in total)
CH2. Social media (EITD + partners')	200,000/month impressions 50 posts/month using project-specific hashtags 10/month project mentions	44,215/month impressions 20 posts/month using project-specific hashtags 8/month project mentions
CH3. Paid advertisement on social media (EITD)	350,000/month impressions 5,000/month number of clicks	191,394 impressions/month 16,839 clicks/month
CH4. Paid search advertising on Google (EITD)	350,000/month impressions 5,000/month number of clicks	174,169 impressions/month 11,048 clicks/month <i>No update. These numbers cover M1-M18 only, as there were no Google paid ads during M19-24.</i>
CH5. Event, conference, meetings (EITD + partners')	4,000 persons reached through events	Approx. 82,500 persons reached through events
CH6. Scouting and synergies with other initiatives	5 successful partnerships created	2 partnerships created (Poliba, Agean)
CH7. Dissemination materials	30 brochures, flyers, visuals	54 brochures, flyers, visuals

ACTIVITY CHANNEL	Expected Impact <i>Overall project</i>	Impact Achieved <i>First 24-months</i>
	10 videos 1/month newsletters 20 press releases	22 videos 1/month newsletter (EITD + partners') 8 press releases (incl. scientific articles, media articles, blog posts)

Table 2: SPECTRO Communication Channels – Expected vs. Actual Impact and KPIs

CH1 Comment: The webpages largely exceeded expectations, reaching over 13,000 visitors per month across three dedicated pages. This confirms strong interest and visibility through web traffic.

CH2 Comment: Organic social media remains the weakest channel, with impressions and engagement lagging behind targets. However, figures show a positive increase compared to the previous report (+33%), reflecting partners' growing contributions and the recent creation of the SPECTRO LinkedIn page, which is already showing encouraging results.

CH3 Comment: Paid social campaigns performed well in terms of clicks, far exceeding expectations, even if impressions remain below the KPI. This shows that the targeting strategy has been effective in reaching an engaged audience.

CH4 Comment: *Numbers not updated.*

CH5 Comment: Participation in events significantly outperformed expectations, with over 82,000 persons reached compared to a target of 4,000. This underscores the strong commitment of partners in presenting SPECTRO across multiple venues.

CH6 Comment: Two important partnerships have been established so far, with the addition of two Associate Partners to the project. Efforts are ongoing, and additional synergies are expected as the project progresses and as links with other DEP initiatives mature.

CH7 Comment: The production of materials has exceeded expectations, with more than 50 visuals and 22 videos already delivered. While newsletters are on track, the total number of press releases remains slightly below target

4.2 Future steps and recommendations

The current set of results highlights both achievements and areas for further reinforcement. Half way through the project, some KPIs remain below expectations and require corrective action. In terms of partnerships (CH6), only two collaborations have been secured compared to the target of five. To address this, more systematic scouting of potential synergies with related DEP-funded initiatives will be necessary, with an emphasis on joint events and shared visibility opportunities. Similarly, the number of press releases remains below target. Greater coordination among partners could increase visibility, for example by linking local announcements to European-level campaigns and providing media-friendly content packages that partners can adapt and disseminate.

With regard to digital channels, both organic social media and paid campaigns require continued investment. Organic social media impressions, though still below the expected 200,000 per month, have shown a notable improvement with impressions rising from 33,000 to 44,000 per month—a 33% increase. This positive trend is a direct outcome of stronger partner engagement and the launch of the dedicated SPECTRO LinkedIn page. Moving forward, this page should be used strategically as the central amplification channel for all partners' contributions, with an editorial calendar ensuring timely and coordinated posts. Hashtag usage, tagging of partner institutions, and cross-posting across platforms will be crucial to maximise visibility.

Paid advertisement campaigns on both social media and search engines have generated strong engagement, particularly in terms of clicks, which exceeded expectations despite impressions falling short of targets. This indicates that while the campaigns are well-designed and attractive to their audience, they need to be scaled up to achieve greater reach. Future campaigns should focus on timing around peak recruitment periods, refining audience segmentation to target prospective learners more effectively, and ensuring consistency of message with the editorial calendar.

In conclusion, while several KPIs have already been surpassed, there remain areas where renewed focus is required. The consortium should continue to invest in communication activities that have proven impact, while adapting and scaling those that remain below expectations. Particular attention should be given to expanding partnerships, increasing the visibility of press activities, and strengthening digital outreach. With the SPECTRO LinkedIn page as a cornerstone for visibility, supported by intensified paid campaigns and strategic use of dissemination materials, the project is well-positioned to improve its performance across all communication and dissemination KPIs in the next reporting period.